

EXPLORATIVE STUDIES OF AN INNOVATIVE SUPERCONDUCTING GANTRY*

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Abstract

The Heavy Ion Therapy Research Integration plus (HITRIplus) is an European project that aims to integrate and propel research and technologies related to cancer treatment with heavy ion beams. Among the ambitious goals of the project, a specific work package includes the design of a gantry for carbon ions, based on superconducting magnets. The first milestone to achieve is the choice of the fundamental gantry parameters, namely the beam optics layout, the superconducting magnet technology, and the main user requirements. Starting from a reference 3 T design, the collaboration widely explored dozens of possible gantry configurations at 4 T, aiming to find the best compromise in terms of footprint, capital cost, and required R&D. We present here a summary of these configurations, underlying the initial correlation between the beam optics, the mechanics and the main superconducting dipoles design: the bending field (up to 4 T), combined function features (integrated quadrupoles), magnet aperture (up to 90 mm), and angular length (30° – 45°). The resulting main parameters are then listed, compared, and used to drive the choice of the best gantry layout to be developed in HITRIplus.

INTRODUCTION

In the framework of the Heavy Ion Therapy Research Integration plus (HITRIplus) project [1], a new design of a gantry for carbon ions is being developed, based on superconducting (SC) magnets. The new design shall represent the next generation of gantries for hadrontherapy, targeting small dimensions, an affordable cost and a credible time scale for construction.

An international panel gathering experts in accelerator design and clinicians at the forefront of research in hadrontherapy suggested [2] to start the development from a recent gantry design proposed by a joint TERA–CERN team [3]. The reviewers put particular emphasis on reviewing and con-

firming the clinical requirements with the clinical staff of the hadrontherapy centers participating to the project and on decreasing the overall dimensions and weight of the gantry. For this reason, the panel suggested to push the field on the bending magnets beyond the state of the art of normal [4] and superconducting [5, 6] carbon-ion gantries up to 4 T. Prototyping the magnets was also indicated as a key achievement, in order to prove the feasibility of the design.

Starting from the clinical requirements, this contribution presents the main layout and optics solutions identified during a first exploratory phase of the development; key parameters are compared and the two most promising layouts are chosen for further development. Details on the chosen optics can be found at Ref. [7].

CLINICAL REQUIREMENTS

The clinical requirements were extensively discussed with medical physicists and doctors at CNAO [8] and MedAustron [9]. The most relevant ones are:

- the beam with the largest magnetic rigidity is $^{12}\text{C}^{6+}$ at 430 MeV per nucleon kinetic energy, corresponding to 6.62 Tm and 31 cm of range in water;
- the scanned area shall be as large as possible, indicatively 350 mm × 350 mm, at least 200 mm × 300 mm; the larger dimension is parallel to the gantry rotation axis. The minimum scanning speed shall be 20 m/s;
- the minimum set of beam sizes at the isocenter shall be 8 mm and 12 mm (FWHM) at the minimum extraction energy; at larger energies, the beam size will reduce following the adiabatic damping of the beam emittance;
- a source-to-axis distance (SAD) of at least 2 m – 2.5 m;
- possibly 360° rotation, minimum 220°;
- volumetric imaging at the isocenter.

LAYOUT EXPLORATION

All the layouts are based on the following assumptions:

- scanning magnets located downstream of the last bending section, to relax constraints on the aperture of the SC magnets;

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Table 1: Key gantry parameters among different layouts (numbered from 1 to 10) and optics: gantry length, radius, distance between end of last dipole and isocentre, number of main SC dipoles and bending angle, number of SC dipole families, and number of NC and SC quadrupoles. The required magnet aperture when matching with varying MF for a given value of input β function or when varying the input β function for a given value of MF are indicated; two values of beam momentum spread ($\Delta p/p$) are considered. The results in the table consider a parallel-to-point matching method but for layouts 3, 4, 7 and 10, for which point-to-point matching is performed.

Layout	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Geometry Parameters										
Length [m]	12.9	14.05	11.7	13.2	10.4	14.2	14.2	13.5	14.05	14.2
Radius [m]	6.4	5.75	5.75	7.3	6	5.55	5.55	5.25	5.75	5.1
After last bending [m]	4	3.5	3.5	4	3.6	β	β	β	3.5	β
SC dipoles: N \times angle	7 \times 30°	4 \times 45°	7 \times 30°	9 \times 30°	9 \times 30°	4 \times 45°				
SC dipole families	3	1	3	3	9	1	1	1	2	2
Quadrupoles: NC/SC	0/6	5/4	0/6	6/2	0/2	6/4	6/4	5/4	5/4	0/8
Aperture [mm]										
var. MF, $\Delta p/p = 0.1\%$	90	70	90	90	70	70	90	70	93	90
var. β , $\Delta p/p = 0.1\%$	90	70	93	90	70	70	90	70	96	90
var. MF, $\Delta p/p = 1\%$	90	163	105	174	90	156	111	162	120	165
var. β , $\Delta p/p = 1\%$	90	168	111	129	93	168	123	165	135	165

- 4 T SC dipoles, corresponding to a bending radius of 1.65 m for $^{12}\text{C}^{6+}$ at 430 MeV per nucleon. Depending on the optics, a quadrupole field may be necessary: this would not be obtained via dedicated trimmable coils, but by an asymmetric arrangement of the coils (left-right taken on the magnet cross section). In addition, the magnet aperture should be 70 mm – 90 mm. The maximum ramp rate \dot{B} should be 0.4 T/s;
- achromatic optics solutions at the isocentre, implying that the spot size and position at the isocentre is independent of the beam momentum distribution;
- beam dimensions at the isocentre independent of the gantry angle of rotation. This implies that either a “rotator” [10–13] is installed upstream of the gantry or that the incoming beam is round, i.e. has the same dimension or divergence in the two transverse planes, depending on the matching method (see later).

Such parameters pose important challenges to the design of the SC dipoles, especially concerning handling the high magnetic energy stored by the dipole for a very small curvature radius and the \dot{B} . Both in the framework of HITRIplus and other European R&D collaborations, several magnet options have been investigated, both in terms of conductors (i.e. Nb–Ti, Nb₃Sn, REBCO, Bi–2212, MgB₂), and in terms of coil layouts (i.e. CosineTheta, Canted Cosine Theta (CCT) or race-track [14, 18]). For design and construction of a prototype the HITRIplus collaboration has chosen as baseline Nb–Ti wound as CCT. The use of CCT magnets have been already proposed for high momentum acceptance proton gantries [19] operating in steady-state; however, in the analysed HITRIplus gantry we are investigating low loss former and coil technology to optimise the performances for a ramped magnet. In addition, the higher magnetic field,

different aperture and curvature radius require a complete re-design of the CCT.

The choice of locating the scanning magnets downstream of the last bending section is another source of important challenges. In fact, on one hand, the scanning magnets must be normal conducting (NC) to guarantee the necessary scanning speed; on the other hand, they must provide quite substantial magnetic fields in the gap in order to bend beams of the maximum magnetic rigidity by some tens of mrad, in order to scan an area of some hundreds of mm about 2.5 m downstream. The specific challenges pertaining the scanning system are not addressed in this contribution.

As done in the optics design of other gantries [10–13, 16], the gantry is considered as a 1:MF telescope (MF stands for “Magnification Factor”). The two beam sizes as per the clinical requirements can be obtained either by varying the MF for a given set of optics functions in input to the gantry (“var. MF”, see Table 1), or by varying the input optics functions for a specific MF (“var. β ”, see Table 1). Similarly, the optics can be matched “point-to-point”, by which the beam dimension in input to the gantry is directly mapped onto the beam dimension at the isocentre, or “parallel-to-point”, by which the beam divergence in input to the gantry is mapped onto the beam dimension at the isocentre.

For every explored layout, monitors and correctors were inserted in the layout, to estimate the accuracy in correcting the beam orbit in presence of magnet misalignment and magnetic field errors. For each optics, the residual orbit was calculated and taken into account together with the *spread* and *offset* in beam momentum to evaluate the beam envelope (including the betatron part), which identifies the so-called “good field region” (GFR). As commonly done in magnet design, the GFR sets the magnet aperture, obtained as 3/2

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